

RESONATE

Resilient Forests for Society

Rooting for Resilience

RESONATE Final Policy Workshop - Summary Report

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Executive Summary

Climate change is a long-term challenge affecting both forest ecosystems and forest-based value chains. Solutions for adapting forests to increasing disturbances and ecosystemic shifts must address the issue in a holistic manner. The RESONATE project has delivered a broad base of research findings on forest resilience concepts, trends, case studies and proposed applicable solutions for practitioners and decision-makers. The team also published three policy briefs addressing recommendations how to better manage disturbances, biodiversity and value chain resilience.

The final policy workshop in Brussels offered a forum to experts of the European Commission, public and private forest owners, industries, NGOs and other interest groups to jointly reflect with the researchers on the relevance of the project for EU forest policy processes. This report documents in detail the setup and outcomes of the workshop.

The European Commission was represented with five Directorates-General (DG): DG Climate Action, DG Environment, DG Research and Innovation, DG Agriculture, and DG GROW (Industry). The EC policy officers delivered brief statements about ongoing and upcoming policy initiatives of the different DGs and confirmed that RESONATE's research results are well aligned with them.

The participants discussed the policy briefs in three separate groups. They gave plenty of comments, examples and suggestions, and validated most of the recommendations. The dialogue provided valuable feedback regarding the relevance and level of priority of the recommendations, pointing out important perspectives from different stakeholder groups and forest regions across Europe.

The impulse talks and statements given by the speakers, and the detailed contributions of participants contributed to shaping the recommendations and further research needs. The interactive workshop format proved suitable to collect many relevant impulses to address forest resilience and adaptation in policy design and implementation on national and regional level.

Keywords

Resilience, policy, forest ecosystem, forest management, biodiversity, bioeconomy, value chains, stakeholder engagement

1 Introduction

1.1 Project context and workshop objectives

Climate change is gaining attention in public awareness, but the tremendous impacts on our forests, and the need to increase the resilience of forests and related value chains through adaptation and novel management practices is less known and insufficiently displayed. Proper guidance and decision tools for forest owners and managers, policy makers and the wood-based industry are not available or well accessible.

The RESONATE project, coordinated by the European Forest Institute from 2021 to 2025, has addressed this gap of knowledge through collaborative research of 20 partner institutions from 12 European countries. The project aims to strengthen the resilience of forest ecosystems and forest value chains to adapt to climate change and increased disturbances harnessing a variety of management measures, providing best practice examples and tailor-made solutions to all stakeholder target groups.

“Forest disturbances are making headlines, but we need better guidance how to increase resilience of our forests and help the forest sector adapt to climate change. Building resilient forests goes beyond trees: it requires robust value chains and engaging communities for a sustainable future. Proper advice to enhance forest value chain resilience are still lacking.”

Marcus Lindner, EFI, project coordinator

The RESONATE policy workshop was organised in Brussels, 10th of February 2025. It has been designed for policy actors, decision-makers and experts in forest ecosystems, forest management and forest-based industries across Europe. The purpose was to engage directly with European Commission staff from relevant DGs, European advocacy groups and national representatives and provide a platform to jointly reflect on their relevance of the results for EU forest policy processes.

The specific objectives of the workshop were:

- i) To inform about the key results and policy findings of the project,
- ii) To discuss the role of these findings within the wider European policy context: What is their importance? What else needs to be considered?
- iii) To synthesise main policy recommendations and research needs addressed by the key target groups: How can resilience knowledge and solutions be adopted, be further developed, and be mainstreamed in European forest management?

This report provides a full documentation of the policy workshop and the contributions of the participants. It summarizes the feedback of the European stakeholders and expert views, to complement the main final reports of the project, notably D5.5 ‘Synthesis report on integrated resilience assessment’ and D5.6 ‘Policy recommendations for improving forest resilience’.

1.2 Workshop setup

1.2.1 Design and execution

The organisational team of InnovaWood, EFI and Prospex Institute held regular online meetings to jointly develop the workshop concept, prepare the setup and programme, and implement the workshop according to the following steps (Table 1).

Table 1 Steps and timeline of policy workshop design

No.	Activity	Meeting, date
1.	Initial concept proposal to the consortium	Project meeting Copenhagen, Denmark, on 13-15 March 2024
2.	Work sessions on synthesis of results and policy recommendations	Final consortium meeting in Bonn, Germany, 28-29 Nov 2024
3.	Announcement and invitations to stakeholder target groups	Mailing and social media (LinkedIn), December 2025
4.	Writing and publication of policy briefs	January 2025
5.	Pre-meetings/ briefings with invited speakers	Online, January 2025
6.	Policy workshop	Brussels, 10 February 2025
7.	Documentation and workshop report	February to March 2025

1.2.2 Workshop agenda and method

The policy workshop itself was carried out in three parts (cf. agenda in Annex chapter 7.2, Table 6). In the first part, the participants were introduced to the workshop objectives and practicalities. They were informed that the workshop is carried out according to Chatham House Rule¹, and that the workshop report does not reveal the persons' identities. The workshop has been audio recorded for documentation purposes only.

The RESONATE's main findings and three policy briefs were presented by members of the project team. Then followed five impulse talks by EC policy officers and regional representatives, to set the scene of the European policy context.

In the second part of the workshop, the participants were split up into three parallel groups held in separate rooms. Each discussion group was facilitated by two RESONATE team members and focused on a different topic. Each group addressed the following questions:

a) Recommendations

- *Priorities*: Which of the RESONATE recommendations in the policy briefs are the most important and impactful from your stakeholder perspective?
- *Relevance & Constraints*: How useful are these recommendations for your work, and which challenges do you see to implement them?
- *Going further*: Which additional recommendations can you propose, expanding the scope of forest resilience to the wider EU policy context?

¹ The Chatham House Rule is used around the world to encourage inclusive and open dialogue in meetings. It reads: "When a meeting, or part thereof, is held under the Chatham House Rule, participants are free to use the information received, but neither the identity nor the affiliation of the speaker(s), nor that of any other participant, may be revealed." Source: <https://www.chathamhouse.org/about-us/chatham-house-rule>

b) Research needs

- Where do you see a lack of usable information for decision support on forest resilience?
- Which topics should be tackled by future research?

For defining priorities, the participants were asked to choose the recommendations which they consider of highest relevance. They communicated their choice by marking three selected recommendations on a poster printout using colour dot stickers. The prepared stickers had a colour code which allowed to distinguish the priority voting per the five target groups (cf. Table 3, Table 4, Table 5).

Regarding the other questions, participants noted down their contributions on Post-Its, which were collected and arranged on flipcharts. The moderators guided the discussion, during which the participants could highlight their important points, provide further explanations to their arguments and react on statements by the other participants.

For the third part of the workshop, the participants reunited in the plenary room, and the moderators delivered a short summary of each group session. In a panel discussion, the RESONATE team members then reflected more on the outcomes and important aspects highlighted by the participants.

To close the workshop, the RESONATE coordinator offered some final conclusions, and thanked all participants for their valuable contributions (Annex chapter 7.4).

1.2.3 Attendance

The workshop was well attended by 40 persons, of which 25 represented the target groups of stakeholders that were invited to actively contribute (Figure 1, Table 2). The participants revealed a balanced gender distribution and fair geographical representation of European countries. A large share of the participants is based in Brussels, as they represent both the EC and European associations or interest groups.

The list of represented organisations can be found in Annex chapter 7.1.

Figure 1 Workshop participants statistics

Table 2 Workshop attendance per group of participants

Group	Count
Resonate team (researchers, role as facilitators)	12
EC representatives (main target group A)	10
European and national stakeholders (target groups B – E)	15
Additional observers (passive role)	3
Gender distribution	21 female, 19 male
Geographical distribution (acc. to the organisations' focus)	21 EU / international, 7 EU countries
Participants in total	40
Total stakeholders (as active contributors, A – E)	25

1.3 Key research findings and introduction to policy briefs

RESONATE, a four-year project of a large European consortium, has produced a broad range of research results, which are published in many scientific papers and project deliverable reports. A summary of key findings was given by lead coordinator Marcus Lindner in his opening presentation (cf. Annex chapter 7.3).

The main topics of relevant knowledge gaps and policy needs have been addressed in three policy briefs (Lindner et al. 2025, Schifferdecker et al. 2025, Hoeben et al. 2025).

Topic 1. Disturbance management. Proactive risk assessment and prevention e.g., against bark beetle outbreaks or forest fires, is becoming a top priority for forest managers. Guidance by policymakers and experts needs to build on holistic European assessment data and monitoring tools to then establish regionally adapted strategies fit for implementation by land managers and forest practitioners.

Topic 2. Biodiversity plays a crucial role in enhancing forest resilience and adaptability under climate change and increased disturbances. Forests with diverse tree species are better equipped to withstand and recover from extreme weather events, boosting both their ecological stability and productivity. Disturbances can create opportunities to introduce climate-adapted species and enhance biodiversity.

These three policy briefs were the basis for the policy workshop, which served to gain feedback from key policy stakeholders.

Topic 3. Value chain resilience. There is a general lack of awareness and unpreparedness of market actors and stakeholders in the forest-based value chains regarding the scale of climate change on forests, and their effects on forest products and ecosystem services. Potential impacts and needs must be better understood by all actors to adapt and to innovate, which requires more collaborative efforts and coordination.

Figure 2 Impressions from the RESONATE Policy Workshop in Brussels: views of the audience, moderators, panel discussion, and networking during coffee breaks

2 Impulse talks and contributions by EC Policy Officers

2.1 DG Climate Action statement

Peter Löffler, Policy Officer, [European Commission, Directorate-General for Climate Action \(DG CLIMA\)](#), Adaptation and Resilience to Climate Change Unit.

His work focuses on climate adaptation and health, the [European Climate and Health Observatory](#), adaptation in forestry, biodiversity, and nature conservation policies. He also collaborates on the Climate-ADAPT knowledge platform with the [European Environment Agency \(EEA\)](#).

- The first ever [European Climate Risk Assessment](#) was published in 2024. It identified 36 critical risks related to climate change and shows that they are growing rapidly.
- An ambitious [European Climate Adaptation Plan](#) is now being developed to ensure that these risks will be properly addressed. A policy package will be produced by the second half of 2026 and prepare also relevant legislation in the field. It is being accompanied by a proper impact assessment and appropriate consultation measures.
- The plan will be an integrated governance approach involving a many Commissioners who have a remit to support this ambitious adaptation plan. The goal is that it works across the board and all the services of the EC, and in conjunction with the [Competitiveness Compass](#). The plan will address three dimensions:
 - *People*: livelihoods, well-being, health, life expectancy, wealth and economic security.
 - *Natural resources*: safeguarding their continuity and provision of ecosystem services.
 - *Climate change as an economic menace*: resilience and preparedness are now framed in the competitiveness and prosperity context, i.e. prevention of losses, protection of assets and economic resilience, but also potential market opportunities for products and services which enhance resilience.
- Forest related issues and topics come much into play for all three pillars, as they are very relevant with respect to natural resources and provision of ecosystem services.
- Governance will be a main pillar, such as risk ownership and responsibilities for managing the adaptation policy cycle, and forest adaptation is part of the picture.
- Finance is the second pillar. Resilience by design must be integrated into all future financial frameworks and budgeting, including mobilising private finance providers and insurance. Resilience is a key element of the future [European Finance Adaptation Plan](#).
- RESONATE results have a lot of good substance, which is very relevant for these adaptation plans, and should be contributed to this process.

2.2 DG Environment statement

Stefanie Schmidt, Policy Officer for Forests, European Commission Directorate-General for Environment (DG ENV).

She works on the [EU Forest Strategy 2030](#), with a focus on closer-to-nature forestry, and is involved in biodiversity-related policies, including the [EU Biodiversity Strategy](#) and the [Taxonomy Regulation](#). With a background in natural sciences, environmental policy, and sustainability, she has held various roles in and outside the EC.

- The RESONATE project synergises well with the EU biodiversity policy, which is echoed in the [EU Forest Strategy for 2030](#); a cross-cutting plan of action to ensure forests as multifunctional and resilient ecosystems which can meet different societal, economic and environmental demands. Many of the findings in the policy brief also underpin the actions in the EU Forest Strategy and its key deliverables.
- From existing data and knowledge on forest biodiversity (mostly from [Natura 2000](#) sites), we can see that the status and trends for forest biodiversity is mixed. The way forests are managed has a major impact on their dynamics. Biodiversity contributes to forest resilience and efforts to improve biodiversity in forests feature strongly in different policy frameworks.
- The EU published in 2023 a [set of guidelines including Closer-To-Nature Forest Management and for Biodiversity-Friendly Afforestation and Reforestation](#). These align well with the recommendations in the RESONATE Policy Brief #2.
- Unfortunately, there is a perception that the [Nature Restoration Regulation \(NRR\)](#) is about looking towards the past. However, climate change adaptation looking forward into the future is in fact an important and integral component of the NRR.
- The role of critical enablers such as capacity building and support is important along with the concept of payment for ecosystem services (PES) to build a business case for biodiversity-positive forest management.
- Striking the right balance between different demands for forest ecosystem services and functions requires quantifiable or qualifiable parameters to set thresholds, benchmarks and targets that provide a knowledge base and facilitate a level playing field for forest industry and forest owners e.g. on actual needs for increasing deadwood volumes or structural complexity so as to have meaningful benefits for biodiversity.
- The EC is exploring the potential of nature credits and biodiversity certification schemes. In relation to forests, the EC has started to look at possible options for the closer-to-nature certification scheme to be included in the EU Forest Strategy for 2030.
- Knowledge on forest biodiversity standards and trends in European forests is fragmented and insufficient today.
- The EC has put forward a proposal for establishing an EU framework for a [Forest Monitoring Law](#) to reinforce and complement national monitoring efforts. The proposal is currently negotiated by the co-legislators.

2.3 DG Research and Innovation statement

Minna Huttunen, Seconded National Expert, Policy Officer, [European Commission Directorate-General Research and Innovation \(DG RTD\)](#)

Ph.D. in human nutrition, research at universities in Finland and the USA, work experience in advertising and the food industry. Since 2013, Ministerial Adviser at Finland’s Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry. Joined the EC’s Bioeconomy and Food Systems Unit as a Seconded National Expert.

- Bioeconomy is a global topic and gaining increasing traction. Today more than 60 countries have a bioeconomy strategy. The European Commission’s international bioeconomy cooperation targets global initiatives such as the G20. Global partnerships such as the [International Bioeconomy Forum \(IBF\)](#) are also significant for research and innovation. The FAO is also preparing a multi-stakeholder [global bioeconomy initiative](#).
- RESONATE’s Policy Brief #3 contains valuable key recommendations. I’d like to add thoughts for policy development and research to complement these recommendations:
 - Public stakeholder engagement is important to advance value chain development. The policy brief highlights rightfully the social aspects, the inclusiveness and the socioeconomic resilience aspects.
 - Data needs: Comprehensive data is key for research and innovation, but we are not yet there. Main data needs are: i) biomass availability, ii) effectiveness of novel technology, and iii) whole value chain data needs.
 - Circularity: How can we integrate circularity into the use of alternative applications used and developed? How is circularity managed in logistics and the new tools we are developing?

Enhancing climate resilience of forest value chains

Key recommendations:	Additional thoughts for policy development & research
1. Raise awareness of the risk gap	1. Public stakeholder engagement , building fair value chain, best practice sharing
2. Increase knowledge and develop efficient technologies	2. Novel technologies for diverse biomass use, DATA
3. Safeguard socio-economic resilience	3. Policies to support social inclusiveness & socio-economic resilience
4. Develop harvesting technologies and logistics	4. Environmental & economic impact, circularity in strategies
5. Address tipping points in availability	5. Descale harmful activities, focus on high-value product development
6. Explore alternative species and applications	6. Sustainable circularity!
7. Prioritise forest ecosystem services	7. Public stakeholder engagement
8. Invest in long-term integrated resilience research	8. Value chain approach, DATA

Figure 3 Summary slide of feedback on key recommendations by DG RTD

2.4 DG Agriculture statement

Tamas Szedlak is Project Officer at [European Commission Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development \(DG AGRI\)](#).

He provided an overview of EC instruments to support resilience. In theory, all sorts of adaptation measures and interventions can be supported by the EU funds of the [Common Agricultural Policy \(CAP\)](#) or through national funds as state aid. A variety of different adaptation measures are eligible for support (see Figure 4):

- Afforestation, creation of new forests and wooded areas, introducing new species such as broadleaf species, enhancing existing forests
- Prevention and restoration measures
- Socio-economic aspects: changing the structure of the forests to improve the social functions and recreational value and/or economic value of the forest
- Nature: measures to boost biodiversity
- Increasing variety of income for landowners to mitigate rural exodus and land abandonment
- Compensation for Natura 2000 constraints or supporting voluntary forest conservation commitments, and preservation and propagation and genetic resources, to have appropriate varieties, species and provenances for restoration.

Public support instruments can only compensate for the real cost, so it is not an incentive. But under state aid, member states have a possibility to pay more for certain specific commitments, such as climate, biodiversity, water and soil.

CAP, State Aids and Resilience – DG AGRI

- Public supports for sustainable forest management cover sustainable resilience. There is no real sustainability without covering all aspects; economic, environmental and social.
- **CAP Rural Development Policy** – RD Programs, CAP Strategic Plans to implement actions needed to build on resilience. (RD 2013-2022 planned amounts, still ongoing implementation)
- Afforestation and agroforestry with consideration of climate change, biodiversity and bioeconomy (€2.0 bn and €27 m respectively)
- Managing disturbances, Prevention and restoration (€2.2 bn and €645 m)
- Increasing resilience and improving biodiversity and social value of existing forests (€1.4 bn)
- Increasing economic value and wood mobilisation, processing (€748 m)
- NATURA 2000 compensation (€ 300 m)
- Voluntary forest-environment commitments compensation, genetic resources (€345 m)
- **+ State aid**, beyond the above in case of specific commitments on climate, biodiversity, soil and water the support may go beyond the costs and income losses by 20% “~PES”

1

Figure 4 Summary slide on CAP support for forestry by DG AGRI

Note: This statement was given during the Group discussion 2 ‘Disturbances’.

2.5 DG GROW statement

Katarzyna Kwiecinska, Policy Officer, [European Commission Directorate-General for Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs \(DG GROW\)](#)

- The forest-based bioeconomy accounts for around 20% of the added value that the overall bioeconomy is producing, which shows the significance of the sector.
- The industry is truly a 'made in Europe' industry, starting from sustainable sourcing through established bioeconomy chains with high innovation potential. It aligns fully with the new top priorities of the EU: competitiveness and decarbonisation. Forest-based industries have a role to play in 'defossilisation' potential; they offer high potential for creating added value in substitution of fossil materials and fuels.
- There are a number of policy synergies where the forest value chains can make the link to existing and announced new initiatives, including the [Life Sciences Strategy](#), the revised [Bioeconomy Strategy](#), the [Biotech Act](#), the [Circular Economy Act](#) and the [Industrial Decarbonisation Accelerator Act](#), among others.
- We strive for efficient use of the resource. The issue of underused hardwoods in the value chain is an important one. In future there will be much more hardwood species/availability in the EU. Today, unfortunately most of the hardwoods harvested are not valorised, contrary to softwoods.
- The key question is: How do we then establish resilient value chains based on hardwoods to utilise the resource more efficiently?
- Sustainable active forest management is the pre-condition. We see huge differences across the EU (e.g. the presented cases from the Czech Republic and from Spain). In some parts of Europe, there are abandoned, unmanaged forests. So a main focus must be: how can these resources be brought into active management ?

Note: This statement was given during the Group discussion 3 'Resilient value chains'.

3 Impulse talks by regional representatives and industry

3.1 Czech Ministry of Agriculture statement

Tomáš Krejzar, Director, [Department of Forest Policy and Economics, Czech Ministry of Agriculture](#).

He has a PhD in tree physiology, and long experience in forest-related international affairs, state aid, forest research and communication. He also has been serving as a bureau member of the [United Nations' Forum on Forests \(UNFF\)](#).

Overview of the large-scale disturbance events in Czech Republic (Figure 5)

- The normal level of felling/removals used to be about 15 million m³/year before the bark beetle outbreak. During the outbreak it more than doubled to 35.5 million m³. At the peak of calamity, 95% of all removals could be attributed to salvage felling. In the last years, about 40% were still salvage fellings caused by storms.
- Regarding forest regeneration, the situation has improved rather quickly due to favourable weather conditions and precipitation above average. However, in 2023 there were still about 54,000 hectares to be regenerated.
- In total 225,000 hectares of forest stands dominated by coniferous species have been affected by bark beetles. These are vast areas, but they still represent only 13.1% of all Czech forests. There remain a lot of spruce stands in Czech forests, which is positive from the perspective of industry, but represent also large risks.
- There have been two significant policy responses: a new [State Forest Policy until 2030](#) and a new [National Wood Policy](#) focusing on efficient use of wood resources have been developed. The policy goal is not to increase harvesting, but to use forest resources more effectively and to add more value domestically, rather than to export unprocessed roundwood.
- Legislative changes to the rules of regeneration and forest management planning are aiming to reduce bureaucratic burdens and simplify procedures for forest owners, allowing more flexibility and freedom also for adaptation measures, for example
 - The prolongation of time period for forest regeneration
 - We are considering to allow shorter rotation periods for spruce and the introduction of payments for ecosystem services.
 - Through an amendment of the game management act we try to strengthen the role of forest owners and state administration in game management to reduce the damage of trees by browsing in areas damaged by bark beetles.
- During the peak of the crisis, compensation payments were given as state aid to forest owners to partly compensate the loss caused by bark beetles. In the second stage, we supported the restoration of affected forest stands, financed from state budgets and the EU's recovery and resilience facility.

BARK BEETLE OUTBREAK AND ITS IMPACT ON CZECH FORESTS

Source: Czech Statistical Office/ Czech Forestry Institute

STRATEGIES APPLIED AND MEASURES TAKEN BY PUBLIC AUTHORITIES

Ultimate goal: to have resilient forests, well-adapted to climate change.

- ✓ New **State Forest Policy until 2030** + its strategic implementing document
- ✓ **National Wood Policy**
- ✓ **Amendments of Ministerial Decrees** (forest protection, forest regeneration, forest management planning)
- ✓ **Amendments of Forest Act**
 - Reduction/simplification of obligations for forest owners
 - More flexibility for adaptation measures (prolonged time limits for forest regeneration and forest establishment; shortened rotation period, etc.)
 - Introduction of payments for forest ecosystem services
- ✓ **Amendment of Game Management Act**
 - strengthening the role of forest owner and state administration in the management of game with a goal to reduce damage of trees by browsing, as a basic precondition to successful restoration of forests and their adaptation to climate change
- ✓ The **state aid to forest owners** was multiplied in the period of drought and bark beetle outbreak (overall CZK 26,2 bill., i.e. **EUR 1 bill.**, was provided in **2018-2023**).
- ✓ As part of it, **bark beetle compensation payments** for forest owners were introduced at the peak of the calamity to partially compensate owners and provide them with finances to keep caring for their forests and reforest the affected forest stands (CZK 12,9 bill., i.e. **EUR 516 mill.**).

Figure 5 Overview slides on bark beetle outbreaks and resilience measures in the Czech Republic

3.2 Catalonia Forest Owners statement

Teresa Baiges Zapater, [Centre de la Proprietat Forestal \(CPF\)](#), Barcelona, Catalonia, Spain

Forest and agriculture engineer with a Master in agroforestry. She has worked in forestry research, knowledge-share and extension for over 15 years.

Overview of forestry and resilience in Catalonia, Spain

- In Catalonia, the most important issue is the underdeveloped active forest management. The forest cover is dense, and the growing stock has been increasing, mainly due to rural abandonment during the last century. Only less than 30% of the growth is harvested. Biomass is accumulating in the forest which can cause severe threats.
- Forestry is based upon natural regeneration and continuous cover forestry. Forests are mostly mixed, but all disturbances mentioned in Resonate are present here.
- The typical mixed forests represent a transition phase: some coniferous species such as Scots pine are dying from drought, which means that only broadleaved trees are surviving. With water being the main limiting factor, it would require high efforts to maintain conifers here. So basically, we are transitioning in the opposite direction, from diverse mixed forests to rather homogeneous forests with lesser species or only broadleaved species.
- Some remnant oak forests were retained in the landscape from long ago, which used to be pasture lands, with large old holm oaks providing lots of micro-habitats.
- The conifer plantations are more abundant, which need to be managed. We fully support Resonate's message that thinning is seen as an important tool for enhancing resilience of forests.
- We also promote the increase of larger volumes of deadwood in the forest, but with a careful eye on the dynamics, the disturbances, the history and the context.
- During salvage logging, we do not have problems of insufficient stock/supply. The main bottleneck is a lack of sufficient labour in forestry to harvest and deliver the wood for processing. Hard outdoor work is not popular, the machinery in use is artisanal and not modernised, because we neglected this sector for decades. We are starting to reinvest, but the machinery is not well adapted and there is a huge lack of training on skills for both harvesting and silviculture.
- Very important for us in the future will be to strengthen associations and cooperation among small private forest owners to work on the landscape scale. Social resilience, including strong local communities is key to be able to react on disturbances.
- More cooperation across sectors is also needed, including agriculture, grazing, and water management. Social acceptance is key if we want to promote new approaches like payments for ecosystem services or prescribed burning for fire prevention.

3.3 Papierholz Austria statement

Dietmar Hagauer, Project manager,
Papierholz Austria (PHA)

PHA is a major wood purchasing company owned by several modern pulp- and paper mills in Austria. PHA purchases a range of timber assortments from PEFC-certified forests and provides professional support for the organisation of harvesting and timber logistics.

PHA is a Resonate partner representing a key industrial player in the value chain.

Perspective on forest resilience and wood supply in the future

- Tree species composition and distribution in Europe will change in the long-term.
 - Spruce will most likely not be available in certain elevations in central Europe to the same extent and amount as today, which is an issue for the whole wood sector.
 - Possibly more spruce will grow in Scandinavia, whereas in Central-Europe hardwood species will be dominating.
 - Performing R&D on fibre qualities and fibre composition for underused tree species is needed, to be prepared for these future shifts.
- Building up more decentralised storage facilities and terminals will be crucial. The huge volumes following calamities such as large storms or bark beetle calamities cannot be taken over immediately, and logistics might run out of capacities. These buffer storages contribute to overcome these bottlenecks. Besides reducing road distances from the forest to the mill it also proves PHA a liable partner in the supply chain by supporting foresters to get out the bark beetle-infested timber from the forest.
- But to be able to handle these large volumes, infrastructure - especially in the rail sector – needs to be enhanced. More loading points are needed as the situation will not be managed by using trucks only, also because an increase of truck traffic is not seen positively in society.

4 Parallel group sessions

The following chapters summarise the workshop participants' main comments to the Policy Briefs' recommendations. Two discussion rounds were held per each group, moderated by the RESONATE team. In the discussion, the participants addressed the priorities, relevance and constraints for the recommendation from their point of view. Missing aspects, additional recommendations and future research needs were also addressed.

In the following texts, the stakeholder target groups (TG) and the recommendations (Rx.x) of the Policy Briefs are referenced in brackets.

4.1 Group 1 – Disturbances

4.1.1 Priorities, Relevance and Constraints

Figure 6 Impressions from workshop group 1

The participants assigned the highest priorities (Table 3) to the recommendations “Support forest owners in the realization of adaptation measures” (R2.1: 13 votes), “Consider short-term costs vs. long-term effects” (R1.1: 8 votes) and “Adopt proactive approaches in high-risk stands” (R1.4: 8 votes). Other recommendations such as “Implement effective browsing control” (R1.5: 5 votes) and “Develop best practices in adaptive management” (R1.6: 6 votes) were also given attention. These recommendations under 1. and 2. were especially highlighted by the target groups European Commission (TG1), public (TG2) and private forest owners (TG3). The forest-based industries and value chain actors (TG4) put a special emphasis on the recommendation “Mainstream newly available information” (R3.2: 4 votes).

All these topics were reflected in the discussion, where participants elaborated on their preferences and provided additional feedback, as summarised in the following.

Table 3 Policy Brief #1 recommendations prioritised by workshop participants

No.	Recommendation	Stakeholder target groups					Count sum	
		European Commission	Public forest owners + state bodies	Private forest owners + advisory bodies	Forest-based industries + value chain	NGOs and interest groups		Observers
<i>1.</i>	<i>Adapt forest management to disturbances</i>	9	6	7	4	2	1	29
1.1	Consider short-term costs vs. long-term effects	3	2		2	1		8
1.2	Actively exploit disturbed patches	1		1				2
1.3	Incorporate post-disturbance forest structures							0
1.4	Adopt proactive approaches in high-risk stands	4	2	2				8
1.5	Implement effective browsing control		1	3	1			5
1.6	Develop best practices in adaptive management	1	1	1	1	1	1	6
<i>2.</i>	<i>Adapt regulations and infrastructure</i>	6	3	7	3	2	0	21
2.1	Support forest owners in adaptation measures	3	3	4	1	2		13
2.2	Remove the salvage requirement	2						2
2.3	Enable adaptation to climate change			2				2
2.5	Safeguard nursery capacities	1		1				2
2.5	Support the establishment of storage				2			2
<i>3.</i>	<i>Improve data and planning</i>	1	0	0	4	0	3	8
3.1	Forest restoration requires						1	1
3.2	Mainstream newly available information	1			4		1	6
3.3	Use emerging remote sensing						1	1
	Sum	16	9	14	11	4	4	58

Note: Each participant was asked to choose up to three recommendations that he/she considered as most important. The counts per group of recommendations (headings in italics) are sums calculated based on the votes per recommendation.

Proactive approaches in high risk stands (R1.4), salvage requirements (R2.2), and exploit disturbed patches (R1.2)

- National regulations often represent major barriers to work effectively with natural regeneration and effective restoration measures.
- Czech Republic: Prolonging forest recovery period has proven useful for state aid financing and gave more flexibility. But both early and late regeneration measures are being financed.
- Flexible/right recovery time window for restoration should be adapted to local site conditions (climate, soil, flora, fauna). Risk that longer heat waves can impact on soils and foster spread of grass species. Acting fast is useful to protect microclimate.
- Limited availability of seeds and nursery material is a critical problem across EU. Should be addressed in national forest regeneration programmes.
- Disturbance areas: being pragmatic, take practical steps to start the transition to other tree species and change mindset of forest owners
- Pests and diseases: not only about bark beetles

Support owners, financial support, competence building (R2.1)

- Resilience silviculture generally cost more. Money becomes available after large disasters for immediate action, but this is only reacting to the problem. Once the crisis fades away, also the financial aid is diminishing.
- There is a large lack of sufficient funding to act and implement these adaptation measures and new management systems.
- There is a lack of funds to take preventive action and take on ambitious large-scale restoration efforts. Effective incentive systems also for ecosystem services are needed.

- Focus should not just be on incentives/funding, but also be on continuous, more structural support and soft measures for forest owners, including forest extension services, education, training and guidelines to enhance knowledge to build up capacity of forest owners in the long term.
- Especially also forest professionals advising landowners must gain a good practical knowledge about forest adaptation to choose and implement measures in the right way. Private owners need to gain trust to implement it.
- Raise awareness for lesser-known topics, like soil restoration or assisted migration
- Available/declining workforce in forestry is widespread issue. Especially a lack of skilled forest workers who are confident with complex silviculture

Mainstream data / Landscape-level planning tools for risk and resilience (R3.2)

- Very important to address climate change issue appropriately. Mainstreaming of data, prioritisation of measures, and proper planning will be key.
- Not just “mainstreaming” available information, but build up a dedicated spatially explicit forestry risk assessment as basis for decision-making
- We also lack a real economic evaluation which risks can have which potential impact in the long term, and where should be the focus: high risk or low risk areas? What does it mean for economic viability of forest management?
- Integrate biodiversity restoration and forest connectivity on landscape level, rather than silo approaches.
- Issue for building data portals and DSS: many forest owners and other actors in the value chain are reluctant to give access to data, for various reasons.

Browsing control (R1.5)

- Major factor across Europe reducing management efforts, big threat for climate adaptation and biodiversity
- Hot topic with many very conflictual views, need new approaches

Nature restoration, Natura2000 areas (R2.3)

- Biodiversity measures and converting forests into protected areas: knowledge transfer and advice to owners how to do it right is key.
- Natura 2000 guidance exists, EC has done their homework. Gap to implementation is that regional and local administrations may be informed, but it does not reach well the practitioners on the ground.
- Practitioners often are reluctant to adopt when it is seen as top-down guidelines from Brussels, so taking in account the point of view of forest owners is also important.
- Conflicting goals/measures proposed from different responsible public administrations are not helpful in the field.
- Increasing number of tree species is not enough regarding diversity. Structural diversity of forests must also be addressed.

General comments how to structure and to prioritise the recommendations

- Useful to point out which target group is addressed or even to group them per target group (forest owners/managers, policy makers, etc).
- Another suggested order of recommendations: i) Resilience of forests, ii) Raising interests of forest owners and managers, iii) Improve knowledge base and decision support tools.

- Focus on feasibility for implementation: ideal solutions or scenarios often are not realistic in the real world, or fall short to take into account the economic and social realities (good example for local complexity: browsing control)

4.1.2 Research Needs

The participants discussed and highlighted various important topics for future research:

- Tree species selection and forest adaptation management systems to deal with risks and climate change: which species/system for which local site.
- Economic evaluation/impact assessment of resilience adaptation: What are the extended costs (including economic losses) for public and private owners and managers for implementing the different proposed resilience measures, what does it mean in different regions?
- Wood products and industry research: How to adapt to changes in wood supply and assortments, what to do with underused and less favoured tree species/hardwoods, how to create valuable products? In the near future through innovation, wood industries will most likely be able to use all sorts of wood resources. Transport costs will be a critical factor.
- Research into constraints and social dynamics, also looking at relationship between conservation goals, productivity and resilience. Socio-economic resilience is not yet well understood.
- Implementation gap: Knowledge needs to reach practitioners, best practices in some regions need to be shared better. And what are the real reasons behind why forest owners refrain from forest adaptation and conversion? Many complex limitations and barriers need to be better understood. Big challenge is that we are dealing with uncertain long-term future, so the decision what to plant is not trivial.
- Land abandonment: More and more forest owners stop to actively manage their forests. This is already a major factor in Southern Europe, will become an even more severe problem with growing disturbances. Strategies and solutions are urgently needed.
- Browsing control: science-based groundwork needed to address this highly conflictual topic, develop new/more effective ways of deer management
- Pests: self-adaptation capacity of tree species
- Natura2000 sites: what are the best adapted tree species

4.2 Group 2 – Biodiversity

4.2.1 Priorities, Relevance and Constraints

Figure 7 Impressions from workshop group 2

The participants assigned the highest priorities (Table 4) to the recommendations “Support forests with tree species mixture” (4.1.1: 10 votes), “Develop training programmes” (4.3.1: 8 votes) and “Tailor your management to local needs” (5.3.1: 9 votes). In addition, other recommendations such as “Foster natural regeneration” (4.2.1: 4 votes), “Offer subsidies or payments” (4.3.2: 4 votes) and “Balance biodiversity and timber production” (5.1.2: 4 votes) were also given attention. There was a fairly common agreement of these priorities across the stakeholder groups.

These topics dominated the discussion, and participants elaborated on their preferences and gave additional feedback, which are summarised in the following.

Tree species mixture with functional diversity (R4.1.1)

- Top priority topic, it is the way to go for higher resilience.

Deer management to reduce browsing (R4.1.2)

- Major priority issue that prevents natural regeneration into more species-diverse forests. Lots of invested work and funding is being lost through browsing.

Foster natural regeneration (R4.2.1)

- Key measure, more biodiversity will help building resilient forests. But it is not always the better choice: in many forests natural regeneration is spruce again.

Deadwood retention (R4.2.3)

- Useful for biodiversity itself, but also as a resilience measure: deadwood as habitat for natural predators that can keep harmful insect populations low

Table 4 Policy Brief #2 recommendations prioritised by workshop participants

No.	Recommendation	Stakeholder target groups						Count sum
		European Commission	Public forest owners + state bodies	Private forest owners + advisory bodies	Forest-based industries + value chain	NGOs and interest groups	Observers	
	Number of participants per target group	10	2	5	5	3	3	28
4.	For Policymakers	7	2	4	1	2	3	19
4.1	<i>Promote tree diversity</i>	3	2	3	0	1	1	10
4.1.1	Support forests with tree species mixture	3	1	1		1	1	7
4.1.2	Foster the management of deer population		1	2				3
4.2	<i>Promote forest management structural diversity</i>	4	0	1	1	1	2	9
4.2.1	Foster natural regeneration	2				1	1	4
4.2.2	Advance uneven-aged forests	1		1				2
4.2.3	Promote deadwood retention	1			1		1	3
4.3	<i>Provide financial and training support for forest m.</i>	3	2	2	0	4	1	12
4.3.1	Develop training programs	2	1	2		2	1	8
4.3.2	Offer subsidies or payments	1	1			2		4
5.	For Forest Owners and Managers	5	1	5	2	3	1	17
5.1	<i>Support ecosystem and economic resilience</i>	1	1	3	1	0	0	6
5.1.1	Diversify free species			2				2
5.1.2	Balance biodiversity and timber production	1	1	1	1			4
5.2	<i>Use disturbances to spark biodiversity</i>	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
5.2.1	Retain natural features							0
5.2.2	Mimic disturbances				1			1
5.3	<i>Diversify your measures</i>	4	0	2	0	3	1	10
5.3.1	Tailor your management to local needs	3		2		3	1	9
5.3.2	Set small forest patches aside							0
5.3.3	Manage browsing efficiently							0
5.3.4	Foster natural regeneration	1						1
	Sum	12	3	9	3	5	4	36

Note: Each participant was asked to choose up to three recommendations that he/she considered as most important. The counts per group of recommendations (headings in italics) are sums calculated based on the votes per recommendation.

Training programs (R4.3.1)

- Training is a major need. It is usually not the first priority for small forest owners.
- Raising awareness and providing knowledge about biodiversity benefits and how to manage biodiversity in the right way (use of natural regeneration, habitat trees, etc).
- Practical down-to-earth measures needed so that owners can adopt them easily.
- Good communication, narratives: owners need to believe in it and feel proud.
- Large regional differences: well established training systems in highly productive EU countries, underdeveloped or missing in other countries.
- Very specialised skills needed for forest work in mountainous and/or Mediterranean regions, regarding the terrain but also the biodiversity.
- Train forest owners also on their responsibilities regarding risks, to properly manage forests so that forest fires don't get out of control.
- Resilience and biodiversity topics need also be included in university education/curricula for the next generation of foresters.

Subsidies or payments (R4.3.2)

- Required to most proposed adaptation and restoration measures, because resilience and biodiversity will make harvesting more costly > difficult to mobilise owners
- Incentives of best practices for holistic management. need to adjust them for biodiversity
- Public officers and private professionals dealing with subsidies need proper training about resilience and biodiversity, to manage funds correctly in a meaningful way.

Balance diversity and timber production (R5.1.2)

- Public forests: responsibility for conservation of forests is often placed on public owners, but many municipalities and public estates depend on income from timber production: need for balanced approaches.
- Payments for ecosystem services (PES) as a possible business model. Spanish example: harvesting companies create micro-habitats as part of timber extraction operations, mimicking disturbances.

Tailor management to local needs (R5.3.1)

- Forest managers: very important to adjust any proposed solutions to the local context, plenty of locally suitable measures needed.
- Policy-makers: “one-size-fits-all” policies are not feasible. EU policies must be general and cannot cover all details, but the varieties and differences of forests, ownership, regulations, etc. across Europe make local solutions and local policy development or interpretation a necessity.
- Also on regional level: Central-European views dominate in policy, but Mediterranean or Eastern countries might have a very different perspective and needs.
- Challenging because regional/local specific policies/approaches can also come into conflict with other strategies (e.g. biodiversity not aligned with bioeconomy strategy)

More recommendations, what’s missing

- “Climate-adapted species”: the term is not highlighted sufficiently in the Resonate recommendations, yet it is the more useful term to link the tree species discussion to the big picture of climate change. “Native” or “local” species (hard to define what is native) or “natural regeneration” are not the best approaches. Climate change is altering the suitable range of species, assisted migration might become very important.
- Biodiversity is integral for resilience and also productivity: it must be highlighted much more. It is not just about tree species, but about all biodiversity, and many other aspects (soil, fungi, etc) are much overlooked. Soils are so important for forest management, but people/owners are not aware, they lack to understand the whole picture.

4.2.2 Research Needs

The participants discussed and highlighted various important topics for future research:

Biodiversity, impacts/benefits of adaptation of forests, monitoring

- Benefits of biodiversity: How can various other species or species communities be used to enhance resilience (predators of pests, improving soils, etc)? Which are the best areas to promote biodiversity?
- Flexible frameworks and meaningful, quantifiable indicators for local level: Indicators for forest management approaches such as continuous cover forestry (CCF), close to nature forestry (CNF), reduced impact logging, etc. need to be further developed and operationalized. Deadwood volume or number retention trees in forests is much lower than a minimum to sustain many endangered species. Indicators would give forest owners a reference to know how much effort is needed to achieve a certain goal, and could be ranked according to the level of ambition. The available knowledge is vague, and debates are often on an ideological level. Outcome-based indicators are needed that are useful for forest managers and can be harnessed for policy goals.
- Build on existing schemes: don't develop new certification schemes. It took 30 years to develop existing schemes (FSC, PEFC), and today only 10% of the world's forests are certified. Voluntary schemes have not been very effective.
- Measurements: new tech/sensors can be exploited. Need to carefully balance the huge amount of data required versus the real gain.
- Regeneration monitoring: How to do it effectively, can it be done with remote sensing? What can be predicted regarding species diversity and growth?

Financial aspects/opportunities of biodiversity

- How to make biodiversity attractive to foresters and landowners? Can benefits be a tool to promote biodiversity? How should specific incentives for biodiversity be designed? Should financial incentives follow an input approach (paid before intervention) or output approach (paid after intervention)?
- What are the real costs? Better understanding of economic versus environmental balance, especially for rural communities. Look deeper into regional cases where higher biodiversity also has led to stable or higher economic returns.
- Valuation of biodiversity outcomes: What are costs and benefits? Which are the right instruments? Payment for ecosystem services (PES), subsidies from state/regional authorities, or others? Natural capital accounting is the right method. There are still inconsistencies between countries, but standardization of frameworks is ongoing.

Specific topics

- Protection versus production: The Biodiversity strategy talks a lot about protection, but Resonate recommends mainly integration/balanced management. Clarification of concepts and common language needed, what are the biodiversity objectives exactly?
- New pests and disease risks: Don't focus only on bark beetle, there are many other pests affecting tree species. How to prepare for new threats? We have very little research on prevention.
- DNA-based tree species identification tool: need for law enforcement in international timber trade. Aim to have a credible test in 20 min if it is a strictly protected tree species.
- Public opinion on biodiversity: What does the public want for "their" public forests?

4.3 Group 3 – Value chains

4.3.1 Priorities, Relevance and Constraints

Figure 8 Impressions from workshop group 3

Table 5 Policy Brief #3 recommendations prioritised by workshop participants

No.	Recommendation	Stakeholder target groups					Count sum	
		European Commission	Public forest owners + state bodies	Private forest owners + advisory bodies	Forest-based industries + value chain	NGOs and interest groups		Observers
	Number of workshop participants per target group	10	2	5	5	3	3	28
6.	Raise awareness of the risk gap	2		3	1			6
7.	Increase knowledge on forest adaptation		1		3			4
8.	Develop measures to safeguard socio-economic	1		2		1		4
9.	Develop flexible, efficient harvesting	1	1		2			4
10.	Acknowledge the growing risk of tipping points							0
11.*	Explore alternative species	2		2	1			5
11.1	Diversification and resource efficiency	2						2
11.2	Innovation towards higher value-added		1	1	1			3
11.3	Promote the cascading principle and a circular	4			1			5
12.	Prioritise forest ecosystem services	1						1
13.	Invest in long-term, integrated resilience	3		1	2	1		7

Note: Each participant was asked to choose up to three recommendations that he/she considered as most important.

* Some participants voted for the whole group, others voted for the sub-recommendations.

The participants prioritised the value chain related policy recommendations as follows (Table 5). The recommendations group 11 “Explore alternative species” received the highest ranking (in total 15 votes; 5 participants highlighted the whole group, while 7 other participants highlighted the specific sub-recommendations). Secondly, the recommendations “Raise awareness of the risk gap” (R6: 6 votes) and “Invest in long-term integrated resilience research” (R13: 7 votes) received also significant attention. Furthermore, the recommendations (R7 – R10: each 4 votes) were considered as relevant.

The highlighted priorities are quite spread across the stakeholder groups, showing a fair agreement among participants. A notable emphasis was given by the European policy makers (TG1) to the recommendation “Promote the cascading principle and a circular economy” (R11.3: 4 votes).

All these topics dominated the discussion, and participants elaborated on their preferences and gave additional feedback, which are summarised in the following.

Raising awareness about risk gap, partnerships and cooperatives (R6)

- Joint advocacy of forest owners/managers and wood industry: in Austria and Germany, the national associations representing both groups hold regular meetings to define joint decisions and positions regarding upcoming policies. To find an agreement, you have to find a common interest or incentive for both sides. Besides these groups, you also need to raise awareness among all the other stakeholder groups.
- Encourage active forest management by means of creating a closer link between forestry and wood industry. Value chain is dependent on wood supply and needs to adapt in the long run to change of species composition.
- New collaborative business models are needed: In Sweden or Finland exist large cooperatives of forest owners and industries, but they are missing in the rest of Europe. This lack of vertical integration is a major weakness. We need to move from cooperation to real collaboration and integration, which means joining businesses and creating new businesses models.
- Other forest products also need collaborative models: In Southern Europe, supplies of main products such as cork, resin or poplar have declined. Therefore, new collaborative organisations have been founded (e.g., Pro-Populus in Italy or Centro Pinus in Portugal) to secure the supply of resources and facilitate the marketing of products.
- Small ownership structure is a main challenge: The large number of private owners (including urban forest owners), small size of forest parcels and high number of local forest management associations or producer groups (e.g. several hundred in Bavaria) are a major barrier. This represents an unequal partnership with wood industries, which is a constraint for more collaboration. Forest owners need to self-organize better and professionalize their activities.
- Funding through CAP? The amount of funding for forestry has been reduced by half, because the Member States set a higher priority for agriculture. We can learn from the examples how agricultural value chains with small producers (milk, wine, etc) have changed over the past.
- Best practices of cooperatives must be shared more broadly in Europe, because forest ownership structures are very different across Europe. Example Aquitaine in France: 30 years ago they had 100 cooperatives, today there is only one “Alliance Foret-Bois” which now sells 5 million cubic meters.

Socio-economic resilience (R8)

- Point is closely linked to the need to establish/strengthen cooperatives, so both recommendations could be merged.

Explore alternative species, new applications, hardwoods (R11)

- Policy Brief #3 is lacking a clear link to biodiversity: How will industry deal with changing sourcing patterns related to more biodiversity-friendly forest management practices (CCF, close-to-nature forestry, more individual tree selection, etc)? The supply will become much more heterogeneous, you will not obtain a certain type/assortment of timber in a constant manner. Processing facilities need to become flexible to handle the variability of the future timber supply.
- Hardwoods and softwoods are two completely different material groups: You need entirely different processing machinery in sawmills, which is bulky, costly equipment with long-term investments. Also the produced products are different, and relate to very different specialised markets. So the practical realisation of this transition will be extremely challenging for sawmills and other wood industries.
- Consumer and market perspective needs to be included: While the forest is changing more and more to the provision of hardwoods, the market demand driven by society is turning more to softwoods (e.g. shorter lifetime of furniture). All international studies point to an increase of demand for softwoods (solid wood products, but not only), while the demand for hardwoods remains rather low, compared to the potential supply. It is also a matter of prices: hardwoods harvesting, transportation and processing is more costly. Europe is not an island and wood products are a global commodity, with major softwood supplier markets nearby (Russia, North America, South America), so it will not be easy to be competitive. We must be careful not to end up in a situation where we penalize our local wood industry.

Invest into long-term, integrated resilience research (R13)

- This recommendation received the single highest priority from participants (7 votes). The relevant feedback and discussions are summarised in the following subchapter.

4.3.2 Research needs

The participants discussed and highlighted various important topics for future research.

A systemic, sectoral approach to the hardwoods question

- How to address the paradoxical situation of diminishing softwoods and large underused resources of hardwoods with almost no market? Today 60-80% of hardwoods are used directly as fuelwood and bioenergy, or are exported as raw timber to other countries, and we expect to have even more hardwoods in our future forests. This is a key question for the entire forest-based sector!
- A broader narrative and ambition for forests and industry is needed: The forest-based bioeconomy is a true domestic industry with a high innovation potential, that relies on sustainable forest management as precondition and can deliver on decarbonization and substitution. It is fully in line with the EU priorities, but we must connect it better to the new industrial policies and the competitiveness narrative from a systemic perspective.
- Dialogue between forest owners and industry needs to be strengthened to find a common ground between both sides, because both depend on each other. A difficulty is that industry plans usually some 10 to 15 years ahead but not longer, whereas forestry takes a much longer time horizon in perspective. Industries are also reluctant to change anything as long as softwood supplies in their region are still abundant.

Innovative hardwoods technologies can drive a shift to more resilient value chains

- R&I on more efficient and new harvesting and processing technology is needed for hardwoods: Hardwoods are heavier, so you need new equipment such as trailers, skidders, trucks and adapted sawmill equipment. Modern harvesters are designed for softwoods but cannot deal with hardwoods which grow not straight and have much more branches. New harvesting systems must also be cost-efficient to deal with smaller volumes and at the same time ensure low environmental impacts.
- New uses and value chains might offer the solution: Softwoods have a large gain for high value solid timber, but hardwoods are a much more heterogeneous resource (e.g., more branches and bark, higher variability of wood qualities). Novel uses such as biochar, bioplastics, textiles or biorefinery products are possible feasible opportunities, but they are mostly still under development and are not yet sufficiently competitive to be scaled up. A major investment into a hardwoods biorefinery is UPM in Leuna, Germany. More support for R&I and demonstration is needed, e.g. under the CBE-JU programme.
- Research with industry is key to unleash disruptive innovation in solid wood products from hardwoods: Example of the Weizer Group in Austria, a major parquet producer which invests into novel high-tech uses of hardwood appliances for trains (for the next ICE generation). Hardwoods is one of the strongest materials, and they managed to reach the performance needed for trains. Today they are also building a large incubator (Wood Vision Lab) for startups to bring basic research until the market (from TRL 1 to 9) in one place together.
- Cascading principle, resource efficiency, circular use: We must address the question what the sustainable limits of multifunctional forest supply are, given the growing demand for many new uses, and that we do not externalise problems by increasing imports to Europe on a large scale. People overestimate the supply capacity of forests. Resource efficiency must be the main goal, to optimise the consumption according to the cascading principle, and to develop also circular uses of wood. Wood construction is booming, and you can already find innovations such as design-for-disassembly solutions (e.g. new joints and connectors, built-in sensors), but the main engineered wood products used (CLT, GLT) are not per se circular. So this must be a main priority for research, because it is a very complex challenging topic.

A long-term horizon for research and capacity building

- Long-term R&I with public support: However, now is exactly the right moment to start more collaborative R&I, so that we can break open these tricky questions in a disruptive way, before it becomes a real supply issue for the wood industry. The topic of value chain resilience is not yet on the radar of decision-makers and funding organisations. There is a need to understand the interactions, risks and synergies in value chains, and how resilience adaptation and innovation can support the transformation.
- Education and training of forest managers and forest workers will also be key: the future forest management will require better trained, skilled managers and workers, to make the right decisions about the use of trees and reduce the impacts of harvesting on the ecosystem. The forest work must be better recognised to attract more workforce, so that we can ensure that we have the capacities for good forest management.

5 Conclusions

The RESONATE project has delivered a broad basis of research findings on forest resilience concepts, trends, case studies and proposed solutions, which are of high relevance to practitioners and decision-makers. The project has published three policy briefs addressing recommendations how to better manage disturbances, biodiversity and value chain resilience. The final policy workshop in Brussels brought together researchers with experts of the European Commission, public and private forest owners, industries, NGOs and other interest groups. The participants discussed the policy briefs in separate groups. Their dialogue provided valuable feedback regarding the relevance and level of priority, strengthening important aspects and further research needs. The main conclusions include:

- The EC policy officers confirmed that the research results are well aligned with many ongoing and upcoming policy initiatives of the different involved DGs, highlighting key aspects of relevance for the EC.
- Climate change is a long-term challenge affecting both forest ecosystems and forest-based value chains. Enhancing forest resilience is a complex goal, and the proposed solutions for adapting forests to increasing disturbances and ecosystemic shifts must therefore address the issues in a holistic, systemic manner.
- The discussions highlighted that solutions must be well balanced in view of stakeholder needs. Markets and consumers are main drivers and represent dominant interests, but equally important dimensions are the protection of ecosystem functions, biodiversity and social benefits of forest resilience, which need special attention. It is therefore necessary to negotiate trade-offs between economic and ecological goals, considering the interests of involved actors. Any meaningful solution must factor in the specific local and regional contexts of forestry in Europe and aim for the best, balanced outcome.
- The challenge is to achieve an integrated value chain approach that can build on science-based, validated methods and transferable measures. It entails widespread awareness raising, knowledge sharing, cooperation support and joint action of actors on all levels. Wider adoption and mainstreaming of forest resilience solutions among policy makers and practitioners across the EU will require a commitment of key public and private actors with appropriate financing for the implementation, including infrastructure development, capacity building (education/ training), and further research and innovation support.

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7 Annex

7.1 List of participating organisations

No	Organisation	Attendance
-	RESONATE research team / workshop facilitators	# persons
1	EFI European Forest Institute	4
2	InnovaWood	2
3	Prospex Institute	3
4	BOKU University	1
5	CZU Czech University of Life Sciences Prague	1
6	University of Helsinki	1
7	Bournemouth University	1
A	European Commission	
8	European Commission, DG RTD	2
9	European Commission, DG AGRI	2
10	European Commission, DG ENV	2
11	European Commission, DG CLIMA	1
12	European Commission, DG GROW	2
13	European Commission, EC REA	1
B	Public forest owners and state bodies	
14	MZE Ministry of Agriculture Czech Republic	1
15	EUSTAFOR	1
16	Forestry England	1
C	Private forest owners and advisory bodies	
17	CPF Centre de la Proprietat Forestal	1
18	CEPF Confederation of European Forest Owners	2
19	SRFB Société Royale Forestière de Belgique	1
20	LWF Bavarian State Institute of Forestry	1
21	CESEFOR	1
D	Forest-based industries and value chain actors	
22	Papierholz Austria	1
23	EOS European Organisation of the Sawmill Industries / CEI-Bois	1
24	UPM United Paper Mills	1
25	FBW Filière Bois Wallonie	1
26	Holzcluster Steiermark (Wood Cluster Styria)	1
E	Non governmental organisations and interest groups	
27	IUCN International Union for Conservation of Nature	1
28	Euromontana	1
29	FSC Forest Stewardship Council	1
-	Other: Observers	
30	Dendron Soluciones	1
31	IFSA SAN	1

7.2 Workshop agenda

Table 6 Agenda of the RESONATE policy workshop on 10 February 2025 in Brussels

Time	Session & Speakers
12:00	Arrival of participants, light lunch
13:00	Welcome, introduction to workshop, practicalities Gesche Schifferdecker, European Forest Institute (EFI)
13:10	RESONATE: Summary of key research findings and introduction to draft policy briefs Marcus Lindner, EFI Uwe Kies, Innovawood (IW) Dietmar Hagauer, Papierholz Austria
13:40	Impulse talks EU policy perspectives <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Peter Loeffler, DG CLIMA: Resilience and climate change adaptation • Stefanie Schmidt, DG ENV: Resilience and Biodiversity • Minna Huttunen, DG RTD: Resilience and Bioeconomy Regional perspectives <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tomáš Krejzar, Czech Ministry of Agriculture: Input from Central/Northern Europe • Teresa Baiges Zapater, Centre De La Propietat Forestal (CPF), Forestry Administration of Catalunya, Spain
14:00	Introduction to Workshop and break-out groups Uwe Kies, IW & Nina Horstmann, Prospex Institute
14:10	Parallel group discussions, with brief contributions by Tamas Szedlak, DG AGRI : EC instruments to support resilience, and Katarzyna Kwiecińska, DG GROW : forest value chains role for the bioeconomy <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Topic 1. Resilience to disturbances and climate change adaptation. • Topic 2. Resilience and biodiversity • Topic 3. Value chain resilience
15:25	Coffee break
15:55	Summary of Workshop results and discussion - Plenary
16:35	Final conclusions of workshop Marcus Lindner, EFI
16:45	Closing of workshop

7.3 RESONATE project summary presentation

Resilient forest value chains – enhancing resilience through natural and socio-economic responses

RESONATE: Summary of key research findings and introduction to policy briefs

Marcus Lindner (European Forest Institute),
Uwe Kies (InnovaWood) & **Dietmar Hagauer** (Papierholz Austria)

Rooting for Resilience: Policy workshop
Brussels, 10th February 2025

Horizon 2020 RIA, project no. 101000574
(April 2021 – March 2025)

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RESONATE aims to generate the needed knowledge and practices for making European forests, the services they provide, and related economic activities more resilient to future climate change and disturbances.

The diagram illustrates the 'Wood value chain' as a circular process. It starts with 'FOREST MANAGEMENT' (including carbon storage, non-wood products, and timber production) leading to 'PRIMARY PRODUCTS' (wooden logs). These are then transported to 'Processing' (factories), which produces 'SECONDARY PRODUCTS' (chairs, tables). These secondary products go through 'Consumption' and 'Trade/Export'. A 'Recycling' loop connects consumption back to processing. A 'Thermal power plant' is also shown as a destination for wood products.

RESONATE: Resilient forest value chains – enhancing resilience through natural and socio-economic responses. Horizon 2020. Project no. 101000574, April 2021 – March 2025.

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Disturbance hotspots and increasing future risks

- Improved evidence about disturbances in European forests (Patacca et al. 2023)
- Disturbance hotspots identified from remote sensing, recognizing natural and human disturbances and their interlinkages (Seidl & Senf 2024)
- Risks are increasing, especially for bark beetles and other biotic risks (Patacca et al. 2023) and for wildfire (Grünig et al. 2023)

Probability of maximum fire sizes exceeding 2500 ha for future climate conditions (Grünig et al. 2023).

Patacca et al. 2023. Policy Brief 4, European Forest Institute, <https://doi.org/10.36333/pb4>

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Operational Resilience Framework (ORF)

Lloret et al., 2024. Sustainability Science, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-024-01518-1>

Sustainability Science
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-024-01518-1>

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

ORF, an operational framework to measure resilience in social–ecological systems: the forest case study

Francisco Lloret^{1,2} · Pilar Hurtado^{2,3,4} · Josep Maria Espelta² · Luciana Jaime^{2,5} · Laura Nikinmaa^{6,7} · Marcus Lindner⁶ · Jordi Martínez-Vilalta^{1,2}

Forest modelling in 9 case studies across Europe

Forest model simulations from 1986-2020 with disturbances quantified from remote sensing data

- Resilience measure: **recovery of above ground biomass**
 - All case studies (except Galicia) were **resilient** when considering the entire forest **BUT!**
 - In areas affected by disturbances – majority of case studies were not resilient

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We need to **enhance resilience** in both forest management and forest value chains

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Silvicultural adaptation options (Willig and Bauhus 2024. RESONATE Deliverable 2.9)				
Reducing stand density (Thinning)	Shortening production times	Enhancing and maintaining tree species diversity (Mixing)	Introduction of more drought-tolerant species	Cessation of management
+ Resource availability + Initiating regeneration or transformation	+ Reducing disturbance risk	+ Diversification of risks + Beneficial species interactions	+ Transforming forests towards a more resilient stands	+ Forests adapt themselves through inherent self-regulating capacity
- Increased exposure to irradiance and wind	- Loss of old trees (biodiversity/recreation)	- More complicated tending and harvest operations	- Few experience with new species - Risk of maladaptation or invasiveness of new species	- Adaptive capacity do not match the pace of climate change (active management required)
Millar et al. (2007), Sohn et al. (2016), Spittlehouse and Stewart (2003), Steckel et al. (2020)	Gardiner and Quine (2000), Roberge et al. (2016)	Grossiord (2020), Jactel et al. (2017), Messier et al. (2021)	Aitken et al. (2008), Pötzelsberger et al. (2020), Royo et al. (2023)	Jandl et al. (2019), Lindner et al. (2020), Millar and Stephenson (2015), Puettmann (2011), Seidl et al. (2016)

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Biodiversity effect on forest resilience

- Forest storm resilience depends on the interplay between biodiversity and climate
 - Species-rich assemblages had higher recovery and resilience to storm disturbance
 - Functional diversity improved resistance and recovery
- Diverse forests with important share of slow-growing species promote higher resilience

Barrere et al. 2024. Functional Ecology 38, 500-516.

Received: 19 July 2023 | Accepted: 25 November 2023
 DOI: 10.1111/1365-2435.14489

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Functional Ecology

Forest storm resilience depends on the interplay between functional composition and climate—Insights from European-scale simulations

Julien Barrere | Björn Reineking | Maxime Jaunatre | Georges Kunstler

<https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2435.14489>

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Resilient Forest Value Chains under changing conditions - 9 innovation pathways

- More innovation pathways for forest management than for the processing industries
- Diversification in forest management vs. efficiency in processing industry
- Leads to potential trade-offs

	Strengthens value chain resilience
	Strengthens forest resilience
	Evidence is mixed
	Innovations that stimulate diversification
	Innovations that stimulate efficiency
	Innovations that stimulate flexibility

Hoeben, A. D., Stern, T., & Lloret, F. (2023). **A Review of Potential Innovation Pathways to Enhance Resilience in Wood-Based Value Chains.** *Current Forestry Reports*, 9(5), 301-318.

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Wood resource supply affects forest value chain resilience

- Overall, industry capacity aligns well with wood resources in three European countries
- Regionally, there is some undersupply of softwood
- Hardwood supply is larger than demand

Utilization of wood resources (EFISCEN-Space) vs. industry capacities (European Forest Industry Facilities Database).

Bozzolan et al. 2024. *Forest Policy and Economics* 169, 103358, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forpol.2024.103358>

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How flexible is societal demand under fast-changing circumstances?

Assessment of demand resilience in 8 RESONATE case studies (qualitative data from an expert survey):

- **Forest recreation and carbon sequestration** appear to be the **most resilient** ecosystem services.
- **Timber production and non-wood forest products** are assessed to be resilient due to the number and quality of **substitutes**.
- Cultural and regulating services (e.g. **ground water protection, soil erosion and avalanches**) are the **least resilient**

Lautrup et al., 2024. RESONATE - Deliverable 4.6.

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Introducing the RESONATE Policy Briefs

- Policy Brief #1 - Managing forest disturbances in a changing climate
<https://doi.org/10.36333/rs9>
- Policy Brief #2 - The role of biodiversity in making forests resilient
<https://doi.org/10.36333/rs7>
- Policy Brief #3 - Enhancing climate resilience of forest value chains
<https://doi.org/10.36333/rs10>

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RESONATE WP X Task X

PB #1 – Managing forest disturbances in a changing climate

- **Disturbances often interact and magnify impacts:** bark beetles and wildfire often build on initial windthrow and drought disturbances
- **Disturbances offer opportunities for adaptation:** recovery after disturbances opens a window for increasing species diversity

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RESONATE WP X Task X

PB #1 – Managing forest disturbances in a changing climate

Selected recommendations

- Adopt proactive forest management approaches, e.g. establishing **advance regeneration** or **reducing stand density**
- Adapt regulations and infrastructure to support CC adaptation: e.g. more **time for forest recovery**; consider **changing species suitability** in habitat guidelines; improve **storage and transport infrastructure**

Recommendations

- 1. Adapt Forest Management to Disturbances**
 - Consider short-term costs vs. long-term benefits: proactive management is more expensive upfront but reduces future damage.
 - Actively exploit disturbed patches as opportunities for climate change adaptation in forest management, using canopy openings to transition to mixed, climate-resilient tree species.
 - Incorporate post-disturbance forest structures into management (rather than eradicating them) to achieve important goals of sustainable forest management (e.g. increasing deadwood stocks in forests).
 - Adopt proactive approaches in both high-risk stands and those expected to become vulnerable in the future. These approaches may include establishing advance regeneration, reducing stand density and shortening rotation periods to lower risks.
 - Implement effective browsing control plans, which can be a decisive factor in post-disturbance restoration.
 - Develop best practices in adaptive management with recommendations for different forest conditions and disseminate to forest owners in national languages, e.g. via forest extension services.
- 2. Adapt regulations and infrastructure to support climate change adaptation**
 - Support forest owners in realizing adaptation measures with a combination of policy instruments, such as financial support, competence building and increased flexibility of regulations.
 - Remove the salvage requirement that is still a legal imperative in many EU countries and allow longer time windows for forest recovery following disturbances. This will facilitate the establishment of more diverse resilient forests.
 - Enable adaptation to climate change in guidelines for nature restoration and in habitat regulations for Natura2000 areas.
 - Safeguard nursery capacities and improve seed availability with the desired seeds for restoration, enabling potential use of reproductive material from neighbouring regions with suitable climate.
 - Support the establishment of storage and transport infrastructure to increase resilience in the wood value chain.
- 3. Improve Data and Planning**
 - Forest restoration requires close monitoring and silvicultural interventions to ensure desired long-term development.
 - Mainstream newly available information on potential future disturbance risks into landscape level planning tools and process-based models to guide management decision making.
 - Use emerging remote sensing approaches to apply targeted disturbance management strategies.

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RESONATE WP X Task X

PB #2 – The role of biodiversity in making forests resilient

- **Mixed forests are key to resilience:** Forests with diverse tree species are better equipped to withstand and recover from extreme weather events
- **Biodiversity is an irreplaceable forest service:** Forest biodiversity is among the hardest ecosystem services to substitute, making its conservation vital for forest resilience and functionality

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RESONATE WP X Task X

PB #2 – The role of biodiversity in making forests resilient

Selected recommendations

- **Decision makers:** Promote management for structural diversity incl. natural regeneration, uneven-aged forest & deadwood retention
- **Forest owners & managers:** Diversify your measures by tailoring to local needs, manage browsing and foster natural regeneration

RECOMMENDATIONS

For Policymakers (regional to EU level)

- a. **Promote tree diversity:**
 - o Support forests with tree species mixture with different functional traits to improve recovery from disturbances and make them more adaptable to climate change. Promote mixed forest with slow-growing broadleaved species and not only fast-growing conifers and support more mixture in coniferous stands.
 - o Foster the management of deer population to reduce browsing impacts: Browsing can be a risk to tree diversity, because deer feed on specific species, e.g. oak.
- b. **Promote forest management for structural diversity:**
 - o Foster natural regeneration in an early state to support biodiversity.
 - o Advance uneven-aged forests to increase resilience and to speed up recovery from disturbances.
 - o Promote deadwood retention and other measures to increase the diversity of the forest structure, allowing multiple species to coexist by meeting their specific habitat requirements.
- c. **Provide financial and training support for forest managers:**
 - o Develop training programs for forest owners on how to manage forests in ways that benefit biodiversity and increase resilience.

- o Offer subsidies or payments to forest owners who take steps to improve biodiversity, such as planting diverse species or maintaining deadwood.

For Forest Owners and Managers

- a. **Support ecosystem and economic resilience through diversity:**
 - o Diversify tree species to reduce the risk of large-scale losses during extreme weather events.
 - o Balance biodiversity and timber production by creating forests with a mix of tree types and structures that support different species.
- b. **Use disturbances to spark biodiversity growth:**
 - o Retain natural features: after storms or fires, leave some deadwood and fallen trees to support biodiversity and provide habitat for wildlife.
 - o Mimic disturbances (e.g. via prescribed burning) as a forest management method to increase forest resilience and biodiversity promotion
- c. **Diversify your measures:**
 - o Tailor your management to local needs: Use strategies that work for specific regions and conditions, ensuring both biodiversity and economic goals are met.
 - o Set small forest patches aside.
 - o Manage browsing efficiently.
 - o Foster natural regeneration in an early state to support biodiversity.

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RESONATE WP X Task X

PB #3 – Enhancing climate resilience of forest value chains

Key statements

Uwe Kies (InnovaWood)

- Short term: Increased salvage logging will lead to market surplus of **lower quality wood**.
- Long term: Climate-resilient forests will favour **more mixed forests** with a higher proportion of hardwoods.
- We observe an **unbalanced risk gap between forest owners and wood industries**. Forest owners shoulder the biggest burden of the risks and face the highest costs.

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RESONATE WP X Task X

PB #3 – Enhancing climate resilience of forest value chains

Selected recommendations

- **Raise awareness of the risk gap:** streamlining adaptation efforts, promoting partnerships, and encouraging information exchange across the value chain.
- **Explore alternative species and novel applications,** including hardwoods.
 - a. Diversification and resource efficiency strategies
 - b. Innovation towards higher value-added products
 - c. Promote the cascading principle and a circular bioeconomy

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RESONATE WP X Task X

PB #3 – Enhancing climate resilience of forest value chains

An industry perspective

Dietmar Hagauer (Papierholz Austria)

- Short-term responses vs. longer-term adaptation needs
- Improved logistics important for value chain resilience
- Research supports innovation in the industry
- Be aware of resilience trade-offs (e.g. set aside reduces resource availability)
- Mutual understanding of value chain dependencies is needed!

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RESONATE WP X Task X

Perspectives on forest (value chain) resilience

- RESONATE established improved scientific knowledge about forest resilience in different contexts
- Different resilience perspectives may not always align
- In our workshop we hope to broaden the RESONATE recommendations on enhancing forest resilience with your views, expectations, and needs

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7.4 Closing session presentation

Workshop conclusions

Marcus Lindner

Rooting for Resilience - Policy Workshop
Brussels, 10 Feb 2025

EFI

Innovawood

pi
Prospekx
Institute

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Program under Grant Agreement 101000574.

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Thank you for the inspiring workshop!

What is next?

- We will produce a workshop report with key outcomes on Recommendations & Research Needs
- Two synthesizing RESONATE deliverables are in progress
 - A scientific synthesis report (D5.5)
 - A report with policy (and practice) recommendations (D5.6)
- Policy drop-in sessions on 6th of March 2025 (Forestry House, Brussels)
 - Presentation of the two final RESONATE reports
 - Time to ask questions about the science behind the RESONATE recommendations
- RESONATE is ending 31st March 2025

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Thank you!

RESONATE

RESONATE project meeting 2023 – visit to CS Croatia

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RESONATE outputs are shared via:

- website www.resonateforest.org
- X account @RESONATE_forest
- EFI's 'Resilience Blog' <https://resilience-blog.com/>
- EFI's LinkedIn <https://www.linkedin.com/company/european-forest-institute>

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- Contact: Marcus.Lindner@efi.int

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RESONATE Communication and Outreach